

Improvement of Data Transfer over Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP)

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Abstract : This paper presents a designed algorithm involves improvement of transferring data over Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP). The aim of this work is to establish whether using SOAP in exchanging XML messages has any added advantages or not. The results showed that XML messages without SOAP take longer time and consume more memory, especially with binary data.

Keywords : JAX-WS, SMTP, SOAP, web service, XML

Conference Title : ICIKT 2014 : International Conference on Information and Knowledge Technology

Conference Location : Istanbul, Turkey

Conference Dates : February 17-18, 2014